

Equilibrium Studies on Lanthanone Ions Praseodymium-, Neodymium-, Dysprosium- and Europium(III) with Thio Acids and the corresponding Amino Acids

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The formation constants of some lanthanones with glycyl + glycine have been reported using pH-metric method¹. Stepwise formation constants of L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid with some transition metals have been reported². The polarographic study has been carried out on the complexation reactions of Pr^{III} with some amino acids have been performed by polarographic method³. The stability of α -mercaptopropionic acid with some transition metal ions have been determined potentiometrically⁴. The equilibrium constants and thermodynamic parameters of some lanthanone complexes with *N*-butyl thioglycollate have also been studied⁵.

The present communication reports determination of formation constants of binary complexes of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Dy^{III} and Er^{III} with thio acids and corresponding amino acids glycine, α -alanine, aspartic acid.

Results and Discussion

The formation constants values of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The order of the formation constants for the binary thio and amino acid system are as follows : thioglycollic acid $\approx$ thiolactic acid < thiomalic acid and glycine < α -alanine < aspartic acid.

The formation constant values of thio and amino acids with Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Dy^{III} and Er^{III} can be explained in terms of basicities of the ligands. Thioglycollic and thiolactic acids are bidentate ligands while thiomalic acid is a tridentate ligand, the coordination being from SH and COOH groups. In case of thiomalic acid, second COOH group undergoing dissociation at low pH

does not take part in coordination. The first COOH group brings in a positive inductive effect and thus reduces the dissociation of the second SH group. Therefore, thiomalic acid is more basic. In case of thiolactic acid, introduction of methyl group brings in a positive inductive effect and reduces the dissociation of COOH and SH groups. This renders thiolactic acid more basic than thioglycollic acid.

The amino acids like glycine are bidentate ligand coordinating from carboxylic acid and after the dissociation of COOH and from the NH₂ end with dissociation of proton. Thus, the coordinating ligand is NH₂CH₂COO⁻. Here, ligand L stands for NH₂CH₂COO⁻ having one negative charge. Thus in case of glycine, ML stands for M[NH₂CH₂COO⁻]. In case of α -alanine, the NH₂ group is more basic than in glycine because the addition of methyl group produces positive inductive and hyperconjugation effects. But both the effects are not very significant. Aspartic acid acts as a tridentate ligand, the coordination taking place with two oxygen and one nitrogen atoms. Therefore, it forms more stable complexes than glycine and α -alanine.

The proton ligand constants of thio acids are higher than the corresponding amino acids, i.e. TGA > glycine, TLA > α -alanine and TMA > aspartic acid. Therefore, thio acids form more stable complexes than the corresponding amino acids. In addition, thio acid anion has two negative charges while amino acid anion has only one. Hence trivalent lanthanide cation experiences more attraction with thio acid anions compared to amino acid anions. Therefore, thio acids form more stable complexes than amino acids.

TABLE I – PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS* OF THIO AND AMINO ACID COMPLEXES

Temp – 25 ± 0.1°, and ionic strength $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaClO₄)

Ligand	pK_1^H	pK_2^H	pK_3^H	Pr ^{III}		Nd ^{III}		Dy ^{III}		Er ^{III}	
				log K_1	log K_2						
Thioglycollic acid	10.16	3.27	—	5.94	4.13	5.55	5.27	5.64	5.39	5.80	5.22
Thiolactic acid	10.19	3.39	—	5.08	4.58	5.08	4.65	5.62	5.42	5.78	5.64
Thiomalic acid	10.29	4.39	2.91	5.89	4.67	6.01	4.05	6.07	5.79	6.19	5.78
Glycine	9.60	2.31	—	4.40	3.74	4.50	4.12	4.48	3.42	4.96	3.89
α -Alanine	9.76	2.31	—	4.57	4.00	4.80	3.60	4.80	3.61	5.07	3.80
Aspartic acid	9.60	3.60	—	5.48	5.00	5.62	4.87	5.61	4.55	5.90	4.84

*Minimum deviation = ± 0.05 units.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Lanthanone trivalent metal ion nitrates (Aldrich) were used as such. The other chemicals used were glycine (Renial, Pure), α -alanine, aspartic acid (B.D.H.), thioglycollic and perchloric acids (E. Merck), sodium perchlorate, thiolactic and thiomalic acids (Fluka, A.G.) and sodium hydroxide (S. Merck). All the solutions for the equilibrium study were prepared in conductivity water. Free perchloric acid, sodium hydroxide and metal nitrate solutions were standardised by acid-base⁶ and complexometric⁷ methods. Metal nitrates of desired concentrations were prepared from the higher molar stock solutions.

Procedure : The potentiometric titration⁸ was performed with a Elico LI 10T pH meter fitted with a combination of glass electrode assembly with standard carbonate-free NaOH in presence and absence of metal at 25° ± 0.1° and 0.2M ionic strength (NaClO₄). All the titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen gas. The total volume in each case was initially raised to 50.0 ml. The following solutions were prepared for potentiometric titrations : (i) acid = perchloric acid (0.2 M; 5.0 ml) + sodium perchlorate (1.0 M; 9.0 ml) + conductivity water (36.0 ml); (ii) ligand = perchloric acid (0.2 M; 5.0 ml) + sodium perchlorate (1.0 M; 8.5 ml) + ligand (0.1 M; 5.0 ml) + conductivity water (31.5 ml), (iii) metal + ligand = perchloric acid

(0.2 M; 5.0 ml) + sodium perchlorate (1.0 M; 8.45 ml) + metal nitrate (0.01 M; 5.0 ml) + ligand (0.1 M; 5.0 ml) + conductivity water (26.55 ml).

The values of proton ligand stability constants (pK_1^H , pK_2^H) and formation constant (log K_1 and log K_2) were calculated as done earlier⁹. The least-squares treatment of n and pL data giving the most representative values of formation constants was followed as suggested by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰.

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